

Bioinstructive Naringin-loaded Micelles for Guiding Stem Cells Osteodifferentiation

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Title: Bioinstructive Naringin-loaded Micelles for Guiding Stem Cells Osteodifferentiation

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Abstract

Naringin is a naturally occurring flavanone with recognized neuroprotective, cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory and anti-osteoporotic properties. In this work, we report for the first time the delivery of Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA diblock polymeric micelles to human adipose-derived stem cells (hASCs) with the aim to augment its pro-osteogenic effect in these cells. The synthesis of the diblock copolymer was performed via Michael-type addition reaction between hydrophilic mPEG-MAL and hydrophobic PLA-SH and confirmed by ¹H NMR and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. The resulting mPEG-MS-PLA copolymer self-assembled into monodisperse polymeric micelles ($\sim 84.4 \pm 2$ nm) and presented a high Naringin encapsulation efficiency (87.8 ± 4 %), with a sustained release profile at physiological pH. Alongside, *in vitro* data revealed that upon internalization into hASCs 2D cultures, Naringin nanomicellar formulations attained a higher pro-osteogenic effect than that of free drug. Notably, these bioactive carriers also induced superior osteopontin expression and increased matrix mineralization in these cells over free drug administration. Overall, such findings support for the first time the use of polymeric nanomicelles for Naringin delivery into hASCs as a valid approach for modulating stem cells osteogenic differentiation.

1. Introduction

The potential of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) for osteogenic and chondrogenic differentiation has been widely explored for the treatment of various disorders including those related to bone tissues, heart (e.g. myocardial infarction), skin-grafts and hepatic or renal failure.^[1]

Among the different types of stem cells, human adipose-derived stem cells (hASCs) have been gaining attention as an attractive source of hMSCs for bone tissue engineering and regenerative medicine owing to their low immunogenicity, immunosuppressive and antiinflammatory activity.^[2] Adding to this, these cells are readily available due to their straightforward isolation from adipose tissue using minimally invasive techniques.^[2] This unique set of features establishes these cells as promising candidates to be used for stem cell- based therapies. Unfortunately, the success of hASCs as gold standard models for cell-based therapies is limited by the technologies used for their osteogenic differentiation, in particular, pharmaceutical-based approaches.

Current strategies for pro-osteogenic differentiation rely on the use of drugs or recombinant proteins (e.g. Dexamethasone (Dex). and bone morphogenetic protein type 2 (BMP-2)), which are often associated with deleterious side effects and limited effectiveness. In fact, the glucocorticoid Dex can increase osteoblast differentiation but simultaneously induce adipogenesis even under controlled pro-osteogenic *in vitro* culture conditions.^[3] The alternative use of BMPs for eliciting bone formation involves significant drawbacks, since supraphysiological doses are usually required to obtain the desired osteoinductive outcome.^[4] Most importantly, BMPs production involves significant economic costs and these biomolecules can be denatured *in vivo*, two major factors that limit their applicability.^[5]

Due to these drawbacks, in recent years there has been a shift toward the discovery of naturally available compounds that can potentially modulate pro-osteogenic lineage differentiation process of mesenchymal stem cells. For this purpose, one of the most promising bioinspired phytotherapeutics is

Naringin, a natural flavanone glycoside that can enhance the proliferation and differentiation of osteoprogenitor cells into osteoblasts and simultaneously inhibit osteoclastic activity.^[6] Naringin offers several advantages in comparison to synthetic pro-osteogenic pharmaceuticals or to recombinant BMP-2. For instance, in comparison with Dex, Naringin is capable of repressing adipogenesis while solely promoting the osteogenic commitment of human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hBM-MSCs).^[7-9] Also, Dex systemic administration is characterized by a plethora of deleterious side-effects,^[10] while Naringin is recognized to possess a wide range of anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer and anti-microbial activities.^[6,11] Recent studies also highlight Naringin's ability to enhance the secretion of BMP-2 in osteoprogenitor cells (e.g. murine fetal primary osteoblasts) and can exert a synergistic osteogenic effect with this osteoinductive protein.^[12,13] These recent evidences therefore render Naringin as a promising candidate for inducing stem cells osteodifferentiation. However, due to its poor *in vivo* bioavailability and extensive metabolism upon administration, its clinical efficacy is limited.^[14,15]

To overcome such drawbacks, in this study, the potential of mPEG-MS-PLA polymeric nanomicelles-mediated Naringin delivery was explored for the first time in the context of flavanone-bioinstructed adipose stem cell pro-osteogenic differentiation. The obtained results indicate that nanomicelles have a high Naringin encapsulation efficacy and achieve a dose- dependent cellular internalization in hASCs. Osteogenesis induction assays demonstrated that Naringin intracellular delivery and spatiotemporal release improves hASCs commitment to osteogenic lineages, with significant calcium mineralization deposits being obtained in nanocarrier-treated stem cells in comparison to free drug controls. These results emphasize the

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valuable potential of Naringin nanodelivery as a cell-instructive approach that can then be extrapolated for applications in bone tissue engineering and regenerative medicine.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis and Formulation of Naringin-loaded Nanomicelles

The synthesis of methoxy-poly(ethylene glycol)-maleimide-thiol-poly(L-lactide) (mPEG-MS-PLA) diblock copolymer was performed by a highly selective Michael-type coupling between the thiol moiety of PLA-SH and the double bond of the N-substituted maleimide group in mPEG-MAL, resulting in a succinimidyl thioether adduct that linked the hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers (**Figure 1A**). The reaction was performed under mild conditions by comprising a mixture of acetone and phosphate buffer with 5 mM EDTA. The crude products were then purified by dialysis and freeze dried to obtain a fine white powder. The resulting mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymers (**Figure S1**) were then characterized by ^1H NMR and ATR-FTIR to access the synthesis of the amphiphilic copolymer. The obtained proton NMR and FTIR spectra exhibited the characteristic peaks of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic blocks, thus providing evidence for chemical conjugation of the maleimide and thiol moieties (**Figures S2 and S3**).

Following successful copolymer synthesis, Naringin-loaded polymeric micelles were then self-assembled via nanoprecipitation by mixing the flavanone and the amphiphilic copolymer in the organic phase. To promote micelles assembly the drug-copolymer mixture was added drop-wise added into a determined amount of aqueous solution ($V = 5 \text{ mL}$) at room temperature (RT) (**Figure 1B**). The physicochemical properties of the resulting Naringin-loaded and blank (control) micelles were characterized by DLS. As demonstrated in **Figures 1C and 1D** the formulated blank micelles ($75.15 \pm 1.06 \text{ nm}$) were smaller than those loaded with Naringin ($84.48 \pm 2.44 \text{ nm}$). This increase could be attributed to the relatively amphiphilic features of the flavanone glycoside Naringin chemical structure (**Figure 1A**). This could explain the small

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increase in hydrodynamic size of drug-loaded micelles over blank micelles and is a valuable information since, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that Naringin has been encapsulated in polymeric micellar systems. We hypothesize that Naringin's bulkier non-planar

structure comprised by hydrophobic (aglycone, Naringenin) and hydrophilic (glycoside, Neohesperidose) domains could potentially decrease the hydrophobic interactions with PLA micelles core. This hypothesis is supported by Sanver on experimental modelling of flavonoid membrane interactions, which suggests that flavonoids such as Naringin may partition in the lipid/water interface.^[16] This is an important factor that also supports the use of nanosized delivery systems for the intracellular delivery of this drug, which otherwise can only be partitioned in cells membrane. Moreover, Yan and his team studied Naringin/p-cyclodextrin (P-CD) inclusion complexes, where computational and experimental simulations indicated that while the benzene ring of Naringin was embedded within the hydrophobic (P-CD) cavity, the glycoside domain was on plane with the relatively hydrophilic outer wide rim.^[17] It is important to mention that the capacity for PEG to form hydrogen bonds with flavanone glycosides such as Naringin is limited,^[18] whereas the PLA repeating lactide units containing carbonyls (-C=O) may provide more opportunities for hydrogen-bonding with the flavonoid hydroxyls (-OH).^[19] Therefore, the amphiphilic character of Naringin could play a role in the interactions governing the hydrophobic micelle core. These insights are extremely important to optimize nanocarriers properties when the encapsulation of flavonoids such as Naringin, or others, is envisioned.

Apart from this, it is also important to note that the obtained Naringin-loaded micelles size (84.48 ± 2.44 nm) is suitable for potential parenteral delivery to bone tissue in the future since nanoparticles with diameters over 150 - 200 nm are reported to accumulate significantly in mononuclear phagocytic system (MPS) organs.^[20] Furthermore, current knowledge of the physiological barriers for bone nanotherapeutics delivery indicate that maintaining a nanocarrier size between 60 - 100 nm might be valuable for improving both para- and

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transcellular uptake into the marrow stroma.^[21] From this standpoint, the nanomicelles here produced are also promising for systemic passive delivery to skeletal sites.

Regarding mPEG-MS-PLA micelles zeta potential, both blank (-13.2 ± 0.8 mV) and Naringin-

loaded (-12.7 ± 0.6 mV) formulations displayed negative potential. These results are consistent with other studies employing PEG-PLA micelles in the literature.^[22,23] The obtained surface charge values are interesting for parenteral delivery, since slightly negative-charged nanoparticles have longer circulation times and are less prone to opsonization by the MPS.^[20]

2.2. Nanomicelles Morphological Characterization

The morphology of mPEG-MS-PLA core-shell micelles was characterized by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). The obtained micrographs indicate that both blank and Naringin-loaded micelles have a well-defined spherical morphology (**Figures 1D** and **1E**). The shape of nanocarriers is known to play a key role in their interaction with cell membrane at the nanobiointerface thus influencing the cellular uptake kinetics.^[24] Spherical particles have shown a significant cellular uptake efficacy in comparison to rods, particularly for sub-100 nm nanoparticles.^[25]

2.3. Nanomicelles Colloidal Stability Evaluation

The colloidal stability of Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA micelles in aqueous solutions was investigated via DLS by monitoring changes in their physicochemical properties, namely particle size, PDI and zeta potential, up to 14 days (**Figure S4**). Overall, the obtained results indicate that micelles are stable after a two-week storage period at 4 °C in both deionized water and PBS buffer at physiological pH = 7.4. The produced micelles maintained a relatively constant particle size, PDI and zeta potential throughout the storage period, corroborating the stability of the maleimide-alkylthiol linkage in these conditions. Regarding the micelles dispersed in PBS, they presented a slight increase in the final PDI. In conclusion, the stability studies highlight a high colloidal stability of mPEG-MS-PLA nanomicelles.

2.4. Drug Encapsulation Efficiency and *In vitro* Drug Release

Naringin encapsulation efficacy in micelles was determined by UV-VIS analysis of the characteristic flavanone peak at $\lambda = 282$ nm. The amount of encapsulated Naringin was extrapolated from Naringin calibration curve in water (concentration range from 2 to 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$,

Figure S5) The obtained data shows that mPEG-MS-PLA micelles achieved a high encapsulation efficiency of Naringin ($87.2 \pm 4.6 \%$).

It is important to emphasize that to date, the delivery of Naringin to skeletal sites was only attempted by impregnation in implantable scaffolds, porous composites or in surface- coatings.^[26-29] These works focused on the development of bone graft materials either to enhance the repair of osteoporotic bone defects, or to provide a multifunctional orthopedic coating with inherent antimicrobial and pro-osteogenic properties. Outside of the scope of skeletal delivery, one of the few examples focused on Naringin delivery by nanocarriers is the recent study performed by Feng and colleagues, in which Naringin established an inclusion complex with water-soluble ternary nanoparticles (particle size: 212 nm, PDI: 0.252).^[30] These carriers consisted of amylose, α -linoleic acid and P-lactoglobulin, and the aim of the study was to improve Naringin bioavailability using a food grade carrier, as well as study the physicochemical properties of this inclusion complex. Moreover, Naringin encapsulation efficiency within these nanocarriers was $78.7 \pm 4.2\%$ as determined via high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Considering this, the mPEG-MS-PLA micelles herein produced achieved a similar high encapsulation efficiency. Such is paramount to reduce the dose of nanocarriers that is required to be administered to stem cells in order to promote their osteogenic differentiation as proposed.

Following encapsulation, the *in vitro* release profile of Naringin from mPEG-MS-PLA micelles was investigated by the dialysis method under sink conditions. (**Figure 2**). This study was performed in PBS buffer at different pH to simulate either physiological conditions (pH = 7.4) or the acidic environment within the lysosomal/endosomal intracellular compartments (pH = 5.5).^[31] The latter was considered important since mPEG-PLA micelles are reported to be internalized via dynamin- and caveolin-dependent but also clathrin-independent endocytosis pathways which results in the formation of endo-lysosomal vesicles.^[32]

The observed spatiotemporal drug release profile was similar at both acidic and physiological conditions (**Figure 2**). Interestingly, the release profile of Naringin from mPEG- MS-PLA micelles appears to follow a biphasic release: (i) a higher rate of release during the first hours (ca. 22% released drug within 4 h), and then (ii) a slower and sustained release over the following days (Figure 2B). The obtained release profile is comparable to the recent work by Yu and colleagues, where the flavanone was loaded into a mineralized collagen coating, containing or not metal-organic frameworks (MOFs).^[28] In this study, the authors observed a Naringin release at 16 h of ca. 65% from Collagen/MOFs and 85% for Collagen coating, respectively. Interestingly, the mPEG-MS-PLA micelles from this work only achieved 65% of released drug after 24 h, suggesting that these nanomicelles provide a more sustained release in comparison with the reported Collagen/MOFs coatings. The authors underline the importance of both preventing an initial burst release and assuring a long-term sustained release of Naringin for enhancing its therapeutic potential. One of the main advantages of the nanocarrier class here explored, is that polymeric micelles have the ability to tune the release profile via testing different polymeric architectures, such as shell or core crosslinking, or by imparting stimuli- responsiveness to the polymeric nanocarrier framework.^[33,34]

2.5. Nanomicelles Cellular Uptake

Nanocarriers cellular uptake kinetics in hASCs were initially evaluated by confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) (**Figures 3A-I**). For this purpose, fluorescent Coumarin-6 was encapsulated within mPEG-MS-PLA micelles and the loaded nanocarriers (particle size: 63.62 ± 1.62 nm, PDI: 0.176 ± 0.003 , Z-potential: -11.8 mV \pm 0.7 mV, **Figure S6**) were then administered to hASCs. As shown in Figure 3A-C, nanomicelles were localized in hASCs intracellular milieu within 2 h after incubation. Such findings were in agreement with three dimensional (3D) CLSM imaging of nanomicelles uptake within hASCs (**Figure S7A and B**). Moreover, micelles internalization and trafficking into into lyso/endosomal compartments was also confirmed by co-localization studies (**Figure S7C to E**). Therefore, the obtained results show that the formulated micellar carriers have potential to be internalized by these cells and can be used for stem cell-based therapies. Concerning this, micelles appear to localize to the perinuclear region but not adsorbed on cells surface, which is consistent with intracellular trafficking studies of nanocarriers in the literature.^[32,35] Such nanocarriers internalization is crucial for assuring Naringin bioavailability in the intracellular compartment.

In addition to CLSM data, the cellular uptake of Coumarin-6 loaded micelles in hASCs was evaluated by flow cytometry (FCM) (**Figures 3J and 3K**). Different nanomicelles dosages (25, 50 and 100 pg) were incubated for 4 h prior to analysis. FCM data revealed that micelles cellular uptake increased with nanomicelles dose in the tested range, exhibiting a 1.8- and 3.1-fold increase in fluorescence intensity for 50 and 100 pg respectively compared to the lowest dose. Once again, these findings highlight the internalization capacity of the produced mPEG-MS- PLA micelles in these cells, thus showing promise for intracellular delivery of bioactive molecules with ability to guide their differentiation to specific lineages.

2.6. Cellular Viability and Proliferation Assays

Although mPEG-PLA diblock copolymers are considered highly biocompatible, investigating a possible cytotoxic response due to drug dosage is a requirement.^[22] Naringin

flavanone has already been described as a relatively non-toxic compound in various cell lines (e.g. MC3T3-E1, human osteoblast, UMR-106, bone marrow stromal cells), when administered in the range of 1 to 200 pg mL⁻¹.^[6] However, it is important to emphasize that Naringin may have variable effects in different cell types.^[8,12] Therefore, evaluating Naringin effect in hASCs viability is important and a pre-requisite for osteogenesis induction studies. The initial administration of free Naringin concentrations ranging from 5 to 50 pg mL⁻¹ showed no significant changes in cell viability across all studied time points (**Figure S8A**), highlighting its non-toxic features. Moreover, the obtained results show that both blank and Naringin-loaded polymeric nanocarriers maintained their biocompatible profile (**Figure S8B** and **S8C**).

Naringin has been described to significantly enhance cell proliferation of osteoprogenitor cells (e.g. MC3T3-E1 and human/rat BM-MSCs) or with an osteoblastic phenotype (e.g. osteoblast-like UMR-106 and MG-63 cells or human osteoblasts).^[8,12,27,36-39] Overall, these studies investigated Naringin-induced cell proliferation by performing metabolic assays such as MTT and CCK-8. However, these assays may overestimate cell proliferation when compared to those based on DNA-binding fluorophores.^[40] Hence quantifying DNA content with specific fluorophores is an important complement to these metabolic assays. Moreover, flavonoids are reported to dose-dependently reduce tetrazolium salts such as MTT even in the absence of cells, which may significantly influence the obtained results in metabolic assays.^[41] In fact, some flavonoids inhibit cell growth but show enhanced MTT reduction. As such, to confirm Naringin proliferative properties, the double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) content was quantified via PicoGreen® in the same samples of hASCs used for cytotoxicity assays. By using this strategy, a correlation between metabolic activity and DNA content could be extrapolated. As shown in **Figure S9**, free Naringin increased the proliferation of hASCs relatively to control groups on all time points and across the studied concentrations. Interestingly, the obtained data seems to suggest that the effect of Naringin on the rate of proliferation increases over time.

It should be emphasized that this study is one of the few exploring the osteogenic potential of Naringin in hASCs. MSCs extracted from human adipose tissue represent a valuable source of cells for regenerative therapies. Besides their human origin, they can be easily harvested from adult adipose tissue, possess low antigenicity and comparatively to hBM-MSCs, exhibit faster proliferation rates and increased genetic stability in prolonged culture periods.^[42,43]

2.7. Naringin pro-osteogenic activity in hASCs

2.7.1. Naringin-induced Stimulation of ALP Activity

Regarding studies on the pro-osteogenic potential of free Naringin, different literature reports indicate different choices for the osteogenic inductive medium. Most of these reports vary between cells grown in osteoinductive (i) [ascorbic acid + P-glycerophosphate] - rOS; or (ii) [ascorbic acid + P-glycerophosphate + Dex] - OS-Dex; or (iii) basal culture medium (BM) conditions. As aforementioned, this can lead to different outcomes in the osteogenic differentiation potential of stem cells. Therefore, initially the osteogenic capacity of free Naringin in hASCs was evaluated under in different culture media (**Table 1**, Experimental Section, Cell Culture subsection). For the first experiment, hASCs were incubated once (t=0h) with different concentrations of free Naringin in OS-Dex medium over 21 days (**Figure 4A**, administration regime schematics). Throughout the assay, cell culture medium was then exchanged every 3 to 4 days with fresh OS-Dex medium. The alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was then quantified by p-nitrophenylphosphate hydrolysis and normalized to dsDNA content by using the PicoGreen® assay.

The obtained results presented in **Figure 4B** show an increase in ALP activity along time after incubation in OS-Dex control group and with different Naringin doses. The ALP activity is the highest at the final time point of the experiment, *i.e.*, 21 days of incubation, which might suggest that continuously exchanging the osteogenic medium with a renewed Dex dose (100 nM) might lead to continuous stimulation of hASCs populations. Alternatively, according to the

obtained results, the use of Naringin as an initial stimulation factor to promote osteogenesis appears to be limited to the earlier time points, i.e., 3 and 7 days of incubation. Indeed, as shown in **Figure 4C**, at 14 and 21 days of incubation, no significant differences in ALP activity can be observed among different Naringin doses and the respective OS-Dex control group. Likewise, these findings are supported by **Figure 4D**, which shows the ALP-dependent staining of hASCs at 14 days via BCIP/NBT substrate. As can be observed there are no significant differences between osteogenic medium ALP-stained cells and those incubated with various Naringin dosages.

However, for the earlier time points, i.e., 3 and 7 days of incubation, there is a significant osteogenic effect of Naringin over the OS-Dex control groups, as shown in **Figure 4E**. At 3 days, the highest Naringin dose (50 pg mL^{-1}) achieved a 0.5-fold improved ALP activity over the OS-Dex control group and a 0.3-fold ALP increase across all studied doses, from 5 to 20 pg mL^{-1} . At 7 days, no significant difference across all Naringin doses could be observed indicating that lower doses are equally beneficial. Moreover, in comparison with OS-Dex control group, an increase in ALP activity (ca. 0.2-fold) could be observed across all Naringin doses at 7 days (Figure 4E).

In summary, a significant pro-osteogenic effect between different Naringin doses was observed at 3 days, while the osteogenic effect between Naringin and OS-Dex control groups was observed at 3 and 7 days. These findings suggest that perhaps constant long-term stimulation of hASCs with Dex, with only an initial stimulatory dose of Naringin (Figure 4A), might dilute this flavonoid effect on the promotion of ALP levels over the course of the experiment.

2.7.2. *Naringin-induced BMP-2 expression*

In addition to the evaluation of long-term ALP-stimulatory activity mediated by Naringin, the expression levels of other osteogenesis-related markers were evaluated to further investigate the contribution of Naringin in differentiating these stem cells into the osteoblastic lineage.

Naringin has been previously described to promote the secretion of BMPs which play a key role in modulating osteogenic differentiation pathways and coordinating bone formation.^[12] The quantification of BMP-2 in the culture medium from the previous *in vitro* assays was performed via ELISA at 14 and 21 days of incubation. The results obtained in **Figure 5** highlight the contribution of Naringin over the OS-Dex group in improving the secretion of BMP-2. At 14 days, a dose-dependent stimulation of BMP-2 could be observed, with the highest Naringin dose of 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ significantly improving BMP-2 levels over OS-Dex and 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ dose groups. In addition, the cumulative BMP-2 levels at 21 days show a 0.4-fold improvement over those obtained in OS-Dex control group. In parallel, cumulative BMP-2 expression at 21 days was also augmented upon an initial dose of Naringin-loaded nanomicelles (**Figure S11**). Here, the highest dose significantly improved BMP-2 levels over osteogenic control group and lower doses (5 and 10 ng/mL). Overall, these results underline that a single initial dose of Naringin was sufficient to elicit an increased BMP-2 production over control-treated hASCs at 21 days. Furthermore, they showcase the importance of evaluating different osteogenic markers, other than ALP activity, because these can convey important findings regarding Naringin effect in hASCs.

It is worth noting that this increased BMP-2 production did not lead to significant differences in ALP activity after 14 or 21 days of OS-Dex stimulation. These findings are in agreement with a previous study by Cruz and colleagues, where they found that exogenous administration of recombinant BMP-2 to hASCs did not increase ALP levels.^[44] The enhanced secretion of BMP-2 by Naringin in hASCs is an important finding, in particular because this bone morphogenetic protein is capable of inducing the differentiation of multipotent stem cell lines

into an osteoblastic-phenotype.^[45] Moreover, Naringin appears to have a synergistic effect with BMP-2 in the total osteogenic differentiation of MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts.^[13] So far, across the literature there are few studies describing Naringin-induced BMP-2 secretion. One study reported this effect in murine primary fetal osteoblasts, i.e., differentiated cells with an already defined osteoblastic phenotype.^[12] Alternatively, a second work studied this effect in human degenerative disc nucleus pulposus cells.^[46] Therefore, the above findings provide evidence of this effect for the first time in hASCs and its importance is supported by the role of BMP-2 in the osteogenic commitment of stem cells.

2.7.3. *Naringin-induced Osteopontin expression*

Naringin has been previously described to increase osteopontin (OPN) expression in both osteoprogenitor (e.g. hBM-MSCs, MC3T3-E1) and osteoblastic cell lines (e.g. human and murine primary fetal osteoblasts), reflecting the osteogenic potential of this flavanone for bone tissue engineering applications due to the role of OPN in promoting biomechanical osteointegration.^[12,37] To evaluate this potential, hASCs were initially incubated with different concentrations of free Naringin and also Naringin-loaded nanomicelles in OS-Dex containing medium over 14 days. Throughout the assay, cell culture medium was exchanged every 3 to 4 days with fresh OS-Dex medium (Figure 4A, dose regime schematics). The expression of OPN was then evaluated by immunocytochemistry.

The obtained results shown in **Figures 6A** and **6B** emphasize the remarkable capacity of Naringin to induce OPN expression in hASCs. In fact, a single stimulatory dose of Naringin was able to significantly enhance OPN expression after 14 days of culture (Figure 6A). Regarding stimulation with free drug, all tested doses (5, 10, 20 pg mL^{-1}) were able to significantly enhance OPN expression by approximately 1-fold when compared to control groups. Notably, incubation with Naringin-loaded nanomicelles elicited a 2-fold increase at 5 pg mL^{-1} and a 5-fold increase in OPN expression at the higher doses, accordingly 10 and 20 pg

mL⁻¹ versus control groups. Moreover, the dose-dependent effect of Naringin-loaded micelles was evidenced since the highest doses (10 and 20 pg mL⁻¹) improved OPN expression by 1.7- fold in comparison to that obtained at 5 pg mL⁻¹ dosage. In addition, it is important to highlight that the controlled delivery of Naringin via nanomicelles led to a higher OPN secretion when compared to free drug at the same doses.

These findings are in agreement with various literature reports investigating the effect of Naringin in OPN expression on other cell lines. For instance, Wu and colleagues investigated the *in vitro* potential of Naringin in promoting OPN secretion over three different cell lines: MC3T3-E1, human and murine primary fetal osteoblasts.^[12] These researchers observed via ELISA assays that after a 3-day incubation period with 3 pM of Naringin (i.e., 1.74 pg mL⁻¹), a 3-fold increase in extracellular OPN expression over control across all cells was obtained. Alternatively, Yin and his team, evaluated the Naringin-induced pro-osteogenic effect in human periodontal dental ligament stem cells.^[47] The obtained results in this study showed a Naringin- mediated 0.4 to 0.7-fold OPN expression induction in comparison to basal medium control, and in a dose-dependent manner.

Another important aspect that should be mentioned in the context of hASCs lineage differentiation, is the relation between OPN secretion and adipogenesis. Concerning this, Chen and colleagues investigated the key role of the interaction between OPN and integrin α V β 1 in defining MSCs differentiation.^[48] These authors compared the adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation potential of mouse BM-MSCs derived from wild-type and OPN^{-/-} mice. The OPN blockade skewed mouse BM-MSC differentiation towards the adipocyte lineage *in vitro*. Therefore, this study suggests that increased OPN expression might be valuable for pursuing osteogenic commitment of MSCs. Besides significantly increasing OPN expression, Naringin also modulates other pathways (e.g. inhibition of PPAR γ and activation of Notch signaling) that all play a role in promoting osteogenesis over adipogenesis.^[7,8]

2.7.4. Naringin-induced Mineralization

In the literature, Naringin has been described to promote mineralization of osteoprogenitor cells in a dose-dependent manner, which is ultimately the goal of bone tissue engineering applications.^[8,28]

To evaluate this effect in hASCs, the cells were incubated with different concentrations of free Naringin and also Naringin-loaded nanomicelles in OS-Dex containing medium over 21 days, similarly to previous assays. The deposition of calcium nodes in the mineralized cell monolayer was visualized by Alizarin Red S staining.

The obtained results shown in **Figure 6C** highlight the potential of a single stimulatory dose of Naringin to induce mineralization in a dose-dependent manner after 21 days. These findings are supported by the work of Yu and colleagues who observed a dose-dependent calcium node deposition from 1, 10 to 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Naringin in rat BM-MSCs.^[8] Herein, the dose-dependent effect of Naringin is clearly visible upon Naringin-loaded micelles administration. In comparison to free drug, the controlled delivery of Naringin markedly improved mineralization of the cell matrix. Mineralization data is paramount for pursuing further applications in the future, especially considering the origin of the used stem cells (adipose-derived) and the effect of Dex in their pro-adipogenic/pro-osteogenic differentiation duality. Indeed, a study by Ghali and co-workers found that addition of Dex at as low as 100 nM in osteogenic medium strongly induced adipogenesis, even exhibiting a higher lipid droplet accumulation than 500 nM of Dex in adipogenic induction medium.^[3] Taking into consideration that this was the concentration of Dex used during these experiments, the above findings provide evidence for significant hASCs mineralization elicited by Naringin, with evident matrix osteogenic calcification. Moreover, the well documented Naringin inhibition of adipogenic regulator PPAR γ , a nuclear receptor that induces adipogenic commitment, could help explain the improved mineralization of Naringin-loaded nanomicelles groups^[49].

2.8. Effect of Naringin dose regime in ALP Activity

Collectively, the previous experiments investigating different osteogenic markers reveal the pro-osteogenic potential of Naringin, either in free form or when delivered by micellar carriers as

demonstrated by OPN expression and matrix calcium deposition data. Yet, in the previous assays, Naringin was used in combination with osteogenic medium containing Dex, which appeared to dilute the flavonoid effect on the stimulation of ALP activity. In fact, in OS-Dex experiments quantifying ALP activity, differences among Naringin doses were not significant at 7 days.

Therefore, different dose regimes of free Naringin and drug-loaded micelles in reduced osteogenic medium (rOS - ascorbic acid + 3-glycerophosphate, not containing Dex) were studied in order to further investigate Naringin pro-osteogenic effect in hASCs as well as its ALP stimulatory activities (**Figure 7A**) in more *in vivo-like* conditions without Dex administration. It was hypothesized that, in rOS induction medium, the addition of a second dosage of free Naringin or Naringin-loaded micelles could elicit different results on the ALP activity of hASCs. Such are important findings for the development of stem cell-based therapies based on the most effective Naringin regime for enhancing osteogenic differentiation.

Hence, further experiments were designed to evaluate the effect of adding a second dose of free Naringin or Naringin-loaded micelles after 3 days of incubation. The obtained results shown in **Figure 7B** highlight the superior performance of Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA nanomicelles over free drug incubation, at 3 days. Naringin-loaded micelles significantly improved ALP activity levels (ca. 0.3 fold over the OS control group), across all doses of free Naringin studied.

Regarding the 7 day assays, different performances according to the administration regimen could be observed for free drug and drug-loaded micelles. For the free drug assays, a single dose of Naringin in rOS promoted ALP activity in a dose-dependent manner, with the highest dose (50 pg mL^{-1}) showing a 0.15 to 0.20 fold improvement over 5 pg mL^{-1} and the rOS control group (**Figure 7C**). Also, a single dose of Naringin led to a 0.2 to 0.3 fold increase in ALP activity when compared to the dual administration regimen, specifically 10, 20 and 50 pg mL^{-1} concentrations. In the two-dose nanocarrier administration approach, all Naringin concentrations were capable of significantly improving the ALP activity by 0.3 to 0.4 fold over the rOS control group, which was not observed for the single-dose

strategy (**Figure 7D**).

Overall, different performances according to the dose regime could be observed for free drug and drug-loaded micelles. In the free drug assay, a second dose seemed prejudicial for ALP stimulation, whereas a second dose of Naringin-loaded nanocarriers significantly increased the ALP activity over rOS control group. Cytotoxicity inherent to a second dose administration was not proposed here because dsDNA quantifications of both assays showed no significant changes between the two dose regimens (**Figure S10**). The above findings are supported by the work of Guo and colleagues, where they investigated the double directional estrogenic effect of Naringin.^[50] The authors concluded that Naringin showed estrogenic agonist activity at low concentrations, but acted as estrogenic antagonist at high concentrations. The interaction of Naringin with estrogen receptor and its role in osteogenesis is well described in the literature, and the obtained results above may suggest that intracellular delivery of Naringin might overcome this limiting effect.^[50,51]

Figure 7E provides an overall comparison between all the tested dose regimen groups, with both free drug and drug-loaded groups. For one-dose regimen, free Naringin and Naringin-loaded groups exhibited similar enhancements of ALP stimulation at 7 days. Overall, for two dose regimes, Naringin-loaded micelles were significantly superior across all concentrations studied. In addition, the obtained results show that dual nanocarrier administration requires lower Naringin doses to effectively improve ALP activity versus one-dose regimens.

In light of previous results, the superior performance of the dual nanocarrier regime was also evaluated in later timepoints, i.e. 14 and 21 days of culture, and compared against free drug administration (**Figure 7F** and **7G**). At 14 days, the obtained results once again highlight the superior osteopromoting potential of Naringin-loaded nanomicelles over free Naringin treatment modalities (**Figure 7F**). Indeed, except for the lowest concentration (5 pg/mL), all nanomicelle doses have significantly augmented the ALP-promoting effect of Naringin over the corresponding free drug

administrations. Remarkably, the highest dose of Naringin-loaded nanomicelles achieved a 0.9-fold increase in ALP activity versus the osteogenic control (rOS) and a 0.7-fold increase when compared to the highest free drug dose. Moreover, a dose-dependent increase in ALP activity is particularly evident for the nanomicelle administration regime. Herein, it can be observed that lower doses of nanomicelles (10 pg/mL) can achieve comparable improvements to the highest doses of free Naringin studied (50 pg/mL), which once again highlights the remarkable potential of nanomicelle-delivered Naringin for accelerating osteodifferentiation in hASCs. At 21 days, however, the majority of hASCs have undergone extensive osteodifferentiation and no significant differences can be seen among osteogenic conditions for both free drug and nanomicelles groups (Figure 7G).

The obtained results indicate the potential of the formulated nanocarriers to deliver Naringin to hASCs and significantly enhance its pro-osteogenic effect over free drug administration, especially at accelerating cell osteodifferentiation and requiring lower doses.

3. Conclusion

Throughout this study, the potential of a naturally available drug to guide cells differentiation towards an osteoblastic phenotype was explored. The inclusion of Naringin in micellar nanocarriers resulted in a high encapsulation efficiency and led to a sustained drug release in both physiological and endo-lysosomal conditions. Moreover, these nanocarriers were readily internalized by hASCs as demonstrated by microscopy imaging. The controlled delivery of Naringin generally elicited a more pronounced ALP expression over free drug administration. In addition, a single initial stimulatory dose of Naringin-loaded nanocarriers significantly increased OPN expression over free drug after 14 days. Moreover, Naringin delivery via nanomicelles significantly improved hASCs matrix mineralization over free drug at 21 days. Taken together, the findings of this study provide evidence that the inclusion of Naringin in biocompatible nanocarriers effectively promotes the osteogenic differentiation of hASCs *in vitro*. Such findings can ultimately provide new design directions for future studies either in stem cell-based therapies or as a novel bone nanomedicine therapeutic agent.

In the foreseeable future, the design of Naringin micellar delivery system could be enhanced by inclusion of stimuli-responsive moieties into nanocarriers polymeric backbone in order to fine tune the delivery process upon specific stimuli. In fact, there are several interesting biophysiological cues within the bone tissue and alterations found in skeletal disorders that could potentially be exploited for stimuli-responsive delivery of bioactive molecules. The latter is particularly interesting since during the onset and progression of different bone disorders many of skeletal microenvironment hallmarks and cellular functions become profoundly deregulated. Each of these disease-specific features represent unique opportunities for nanocarrier-mediated stimuli-responsive release of therapeutics. This spatiotemporally controlled drug release can result in higher stability *in vivo* and improved biodistribution of the drug at skeletal sites upon parenteral administration. The combination of bioinspired

therapeutics with design advances in nanocarriers performance, will undoubtedly pave the future in providing suitable candidates for future commercialization and realistic clinical application.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Methoxy-poly(ethylene glycol)-maleimide (mPEG-MAL) (Mn 5000, > 90 % purity), thiol-poly(L-lactide) (PLA-SH) (Mn 5000, PDI < 1.2); 4-Nitrophenyl phosphate disodium salt hexahydrate (4NPhP), 4-Nitrophenol 10 mM (4NPh), phosphate buffered saline (PBS), formaldehyde, Coumarin-6, Naringin (> 95 % purity), P-glycerophosphate disodium salt hydrate, Alizarin Red S, Triton X-100 and Amicon® Ultra-4 mL (3000 MWCO) were all purchased from Laborspirit (Lisbon, Portugal). Spectra/Por 1 dialysis tubing (6000 - 8000 Da MWCO) and Float-A-Lyzer G2 (3500 - 5000 Da MWCO) dialysis cassettes were purchased from Reagente 5 (Oporto, Portugal). Human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hASCs, *Homo Sapiens*, ATCC® PCS-500-011™) were purchased from LGC Standards S.L.U. (Barcelona, Spain). Minimum Essential Medium a-modification (a-MEM), fetal bovine serum (FBS, E.U. approved, South American origin), antibiotic, TrypLE™ Xpress Enzyme with phenol red (1X), Quant-iT™ PicoGreen® dsDNA Assay Kit, AlamarBlue™, 1-Step™ NBT/BCIP Substrate Solution, and Wheat Germ Agglutinin (WGA) Alexa Fluor® 594 conjugate dye and DAPI were purchased from Alfacene (Lisbon, Portugal). Dexamethasone (Dex, 96% purity) and Dulbecco's PBS were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Oeiras, Portugal). L-ascorbic acid 2-phosphate magnesium salt was purchased from VWR (Lisbon, Portugal).

Synthesis of mPEG-MS-PLA Copolymer: mPEG-MS-PLA copolymer was synthesized via a Michael-type addition reaction between mPEG-MAL and PLA-SH (Figure S1).^[52] Briefly, mPEG-MAL (1.5 mPEG/PLA molar ratio, 0.04 mmol) and PLA-SH (0.0267 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture of acetone (v/v = 0.43) and sodium phosphate buffer (pH = 7.2, 100 mM,

v/v = 0.57) containing EDTA (5 mM) and mixed under inert conditions (N₂) for 2 days at RT. Afterwards, the resulting crude mixture was completely dried in a rotary evaporator (Buchi, Rotavapor® R-300), dissolved in dichloromethane and then precipitated in cold diethyl ether. The recovered precipitate was then dialyzed (6000 - 8000 Da MWCO) against deionized water for 72 h, before being frozen at -80 °C and freeze-dried for storage.

Spectroscopy Characterization of mPEG-MS-PLA Copolymer: The successful synthesis of mPEG-MS-PLA was characterized by different spectroscopy techniques. Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance III 400 MHz spectrometer. Prior to spectra acquisition, samples were dissolved in CDCl₃ and transferred to 300 MHz NMR glass tubes (Sigma-Aldrich, Sintra, Portugal). NMR spectra were acquired with 18 s relaxation delay, 256 scans and 32 dummy scans. Data processing was performed in the MestReNova v6.0.2 software, and spectra were normalized according to the established CDCl₃ solvent peak at 7.26 ppm. Fourier Transformed Infrared spectra were collected on dried powder samples with attenuated total reflectance (ATR-FTIR) by using a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer. The spectra of all samples were recorded at a 4 cm⁻¹ resolution with a total of 256 scans in the spectral width of 4000 to 350 cm⁻¹. Spectral data was processed in OPUS software.

Preparation of mPEG-MS-PLA Nanomicelles: Self-assembly of Naringin-loaded or blank mPEG-MS-PLA nanomicelles was performed by nanoprecipitation. First, the copolymer (5 mg) was dissolved in 1 mL of freshly prepared acetone solution containing Naringin (10 % w/w of copolymer) under ultrasound sonication for 5 min. Then, the solution was added dropwise into a 10 mL round-bottom flask containing 5 mL deionized water and stirred for 90 min at 400 rpm, RT. Afterwards, acetone was evaporated under a rotary evaporator during 8 min (37 °C, 50 mbar). The resultant solution was dialyzed (3500 -5000 Da MWCO) against deionized water for 1 h to remove free Naringin. Blank micelles were prepared following the above-mentioned procedure without dialysis.

Physicochemical Characterization of Nanomicelles: The average hydrodynamic particle radius (Hr), size distribution (PDI) and (ζ -potential of the different micelles (1 mg mL^{-1}) were characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS) with a Zetasizer Nano ZS equipment (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, UK). All measurements were carried out in triplicate at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and with a 173° backscatter angle. Nanomicelles morphology was observed by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). Samples were prepared by drop-wise addition of 10 pL of freshly prepared micelles (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) on a carbon-film copper grid and left to dry overnight, at RT. STEM micrographs were acquired in a Hitachi SU-70 STEM microscope, operated at an accelerating voltage of 20.0 kV .

Evaluation of Nanomicelles Colloidal Stability: Nanomicelles colloidal stability was investigated by monitoring changes in size, PDI and (ζ -potential along time upon storage in solution. For stability studies Naringin-loaded nanocarrier formulations ($n=3$), were prepared by nanoprecipitation and maintained in deionized water or PBS ($\text{pH} = 7.4$) at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Nanomicelles and their physicochemical properties were then analyzed by DLS at different time intervals: 0, 1, 7 and 14 days.

Drug Loading: Naringin encapsulation efficiency was determined by ultraviolet-visible (UV-VIS) absorbance of the flavanone peak of Naringin ($\lambda = 282 \text{ nm}$) corresponding to the benzoyl moiety. This peak is followed by a another region of smaller intensity to higher wavelengths ($300 - 400 \text{ nm}$), associated with the cinnamoyl moiety and is characteristic of flavanones such as Naringin (**Figure S5A1**).^[53] Briefly, after free drug removal, Naringin-loaded nanomicelles solution (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) was analyzed by UV-VIS at 282 nm . Blank nanomicelles (0.2 mg mL^{-1}) established the blank for UV-VIS quantification. The UV-VIS absorbance was measured in a microplate reader equipped with a tungsten halogen lamp (Synergy HTX Biotek, Izasa Scientific, Carnaxide, Portugal) by using a quartz microplate (Hella transparent 96-wellplate, VWR, Lisbon, Portugal). A standard calibration curve of

Naringin in deionized water was used to determine the drug encapsulation efficacy (**Figure S5**).

Encapsulation efficiency was calculated using the below formula:

Encapsulation Efficiency (%):

$$\frac{\text{Amount of Naringin within the micelles}}{\text{Theoretical amount of Naringin added}} \times 100$$

In vitro Drug Release Profile: The *in vitro* Naringin release profile was investigated in PBS at various pH conditions to mimic different physiological scenarios: pH 7.4 (physiological pH) and pH 5.5 (endo-lysosomal pH). Briefly, 2 mL of freshly prepared Naringin-loaded micelles (1 mg mL⁻¹) were transferred to a dialysis tubing (3500 - 5000 Da MWCO) and submerged in 15 mL of PBS at 37 °C at a constant stirring rate (600 rpm). At defined time intervals, 1 mL samples were withdrawn from the dialysate and replaced with the same volume of fresh PBS. Samples were withdrawn at different time points until the plateau phase was achieved. For this study, the standard calibration curve of the drug in water was used (Figure S5).

Cell Culture: Cells were manipulated within a Class II biological safety cabinet and maintained as per established guidelines in a humidified 5 % CO₂ atmosphere incubator with 95 % O₂ and at 37 °C. ^[54] hASCs were routinely cultured in α-MEM supplemented with 10 % (v/v) heat-inactivated FBS and 1 % of antibiotic mixture (basal growth medium, BM) and media was exchanged every 5 days. Cells were subcultured before reaching confluence. All plastic adherent well plates were made of tissue culture treated polystyrene (Sarstedt, Sintra, Portugal). For cellular experiments investigating osteogenic differentiation, ascorbic acid, 0- glycerophosphate and Dex stock solutions were prepared in dPBS and frozen at -20°C. Different osteogenic media were prepared from such aliquots. Osteogenic supplements were added to BM in the following concentrations: (i) reduced osteogenic differentiation medium (rOS) - 50 pg mL⁻¹ ascorbic acid and 10 mM P-glycerophosphate; and (ii) OS-Dex - rOS and 100 nM Dex.

For preparation of free Naringin concentrations, the drug was initially dissolved in sterile

dimethylsulfoxide (50 mg mL⁻¹) and subsequently diluted in the respective assay media (basal or osteogenic) and to a final 0.1 % (v/v) dimethylsulfoxide content across all concentrations. Osteogenic assays involving alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity and BMP-2 quantifications, as well as OPN and Alizarin Red S visualization followed the below described conditions (Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of the conditions used in osteogenic differentiation assays.

Assay*	Culture medium	Pharmaceutic	Dosing regime	Total incubation time (days)
I, OS-Dex	Ascorbic acid + P-glycerophosphate + Dex (OS)	Naringin	Single	21
II, One dose	Ascorbic acid + P-glycerophosphate (rOS)	Naringin; Naringin-loaded micelles	Single	7
II, Two dose	Ascorbic acid + P-glycerophosphate (rOS)	Naringin; Naringin-loaded micelles	Double	7, 14, 21

ⁱⁱ Across all experiments, medium was exchanged every 3 days containing the respective osteogenic supplements listed above, except for the Two dose assay, where medium with a second dose of pharmaceutic was added after 3 days. Please see the corresponding dose regimen schematics in each result panel.

In vitro Cellular Uptake Studies: Nanomicelles cellular uptake kinetics in hASCs were evaluated via fluorescence microscopy. Briefly, hASCs were seeded in p-Slide 8-well chambers (ibidi GmbH) overnight at a density of 8.0 and 25.0 x 10³ cells well⁻¹, respectively, in free- antibiotic BM. Then, cells were incubated with 250 pg well⁻¹ of Coumarin-6-loaded nanocarriers for different time intervals (2, 4 and 6 h). After each time point, cells were fixed in 4% formaldehyde. After 6 h, fixed cells were washed three times with dPBS and then the cells cytoplasm was labelled with 50 pL of WGA Alexa Fluor® 594 conjugate dye (0.2 mg mL⁻¹) by incubating for 5 min in the dark. Afterwards, cells were rinsed three times in dPBS and maintained in dPBS until fluorescence microscopy analysis. CLSM and fluorescence microscopy (Axio Imager 2, Zeiss) were used to follow the kinetics of intracellular internalization of the nanocarriers. Image processing was performed using ZEN v2.3 blue

edition software (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH). Alternatively, the quantitative measurement of

Coumarin-6 fluorescence intensity was conducted using a flow cytometer. hASCs were seeded in 24-well plates overnight at a density of 50 and 40 x 10³ cells well⁻¹ (n=4) respectively, in free-antibiotic BM. Then, cells were incubated with the 96-well plate equivalent of 25, 50 and 100 pg of Coumarin-6-nanocarriers per well. Nanocarriers were previously concentrated by centrifuging for 30 min in Amicon® ultra centrifugal units (3000 Da MWCO) at 16600 g. After 4 h incubation, cells were washed twice with dPBS, trypsinized (500 pL, 5 min incubation at 37°C), neutralized with equal volume of dPBS and collected by centrifugation at 500 g for 5 min. Then, the supernatant was aspirated and cells were suspended in 200 pL of dPBS prior to fluorescent intensity measurements.

Cytotoxicity and Cellular Proliferation Assays: Assessment of hASCs cell metabolism was performed by using the AlamarBlue® Cell Viability assay. Briefly, hASCs were seeded at a density of 3.5 x 10³ cells well⁻¹ (n=5) in a 96-well plate overnight in BM. Then, cells were incubated with BM containing free Naringin or Naringin-loaded micelles at a final drug concentration of 0 (K-, negative control), 5, 10, 20 and 50 pg mL⁻¹ of Naringin. For blank and Naringin-loaded micelles cytotoxicity evaluation, nanocarriers were concentrated in BM and diluted according to the different tested concentrations. For blank micelles experiments, cells were incubated with BM containing nanocarrier dosages of 25, 50, 75, 100, 200 pg nanocarriers well⁻¹. For these assays, and different Naringin concentrations of 0 (K-, control), 5, 10, 20 and 50 pg mL⁻¹ were used. During the assays, all cells were incubated for 24, 48 and 72 h. After each timepoint, the medium was exchanged to BM containing AlamarBlue according to manufacturer's instructions. Following an overnight incubation period, the media was then transferred to a black clear bottom 96-well plate for analysis. AlamarBlue fluorescence was detected at an excitation/emission of $\lambda_{ex} = 540 \text{ nm}$ / $\lambda_{em} = 600 \text{ nm}$ by using a multi-mode microplate reader. All conditions were normalized to the control group (BM) set at 100 %

viability. Then, samples from the previous cytotoxicity assays (regarding free drug groups) were rinsed with dPBS, incubated with 200 pL of 2 % Triton X-100 in deionized water and sonicated for 7 min

before plates were frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This freeze-thaw cycle was repeated one more time before determining lysates dsDNA content with the PicoGreen kit according to the manufacturer's instructions. Cell dsDNA content was then determined after incubation for 5 min in the dark at RT. The samples were excited at $\lambda = 485\text{ nm}$ and fluorescence intensity was measured at $\lambda = 520\text{ nm}$ in a microplate reader.

ALP Activity Measurement Assays: The ability of Naringin to induce osteogenic differentiation of hASCs was evaluated in OS-Dex or rOS. hASCs were seeded overnight in a 48-well plate at a density of $3.5 \times 10^3\text{ cells well}^{-1}$ ($n=4$) in BM. Then, medium was replaced with BM and OS-Dex containing free Naringin or Naringin-loaded polymeric nanomicelles at a concentration of 0 (control), 5, 10, 20 and $50\text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Naringin, accordingly. All cells were incubated for 3, 7, 14 and 21 days and the respective differentiation medium was exchanged every 3 to 4 days. After each time point, cells were washed twice with dPBS and incubated with 300 μL of 2 % Triton X-100 solution in an ultrasound bath for 7 min (37 Hz, sweep field, 60% potency) before being frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This freeze-thaw cycle was repeated one more time before determining ALP activity in the lysates by using 4NPhP ALP-mediated hydrolysis to quantify 4NPh release. For this quantification, 25 μL of each lysate sample were added to 75 μL of a freshly prepared 4NPhP solution (2 mg mL^{-1}) in 1 M diethanolamine (DEA) buffer (pH 9.8, with 0.5 mM MgCl₂). The samples were incubated in the dark at 37°C for 1 h. Enzyme activity was then quantified by UV-VIS analysis at $\lambda = 405\text{ nm}$. A standard curve of 4NPh was used as reference (0, 15, 30, 50, 75, 95 μM in DEA buffer). ALP activity was normalized according to the total DNA content in cell lysate determined by a PicoGreen® DNA Quantification kit according to the aforementioned protocol, and ALP was expressed as nanomole of p-nitrophenol $\mu\text{g DNA}^{-1}$.

ALP Staining: To visualize the ALP activity in the cell monolayer, cells were stained with 1-Step™ NBT/BCIP Substrate Solution. Briefly, hASCs were seeded overnight in 48-well plates at a density of 3.5×10^3 cells well⁻¹ (n=3) in BM. Then, cells were treated with BM and OS-Dex containing free Naringin or Naringin-loaded polymeric nanomicelles at a concentration of 0 (K-, control), 5, 10, 20 and 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Naringin. Cells were incubated for 14 days and differentiation medium was exchanged every 3 to 4 days. After each timepoint, cells were fixed as aforementioned and rinsed in dPBS before adding 200 μL of NBT/BCIP and incubating for 1 h at 37 °C. Stained cells were imaged with a Stemi 508 Stereo Microscope (Zeiss, Taper, Sintra, Portugal).

ELISA Immunoassay Quantification of BMP-2 Secretion: BMP-2 secretion from hASCs was determined via ELISA kit for human BMP-2 according to the manufacturer's instructions. For this assay, culture medium from the ALP activity experiments with OS-Dex at 14 and 21 days was collected and frozen at -20°C. Then, BMP-2 levels were quantified by UV-VIS analysis at $X = 450$ nm with the absorbance measured at $X = 550$ nm serving as correction factor by using a microplate reader. BMP-2 levels were expressed in pg mL^{-1} of BMP-2 normalized to dsDNA content.

Osteopontin Immunostaining: Osteopontin (OPN) expression was visualized via

fluorescence imaging of the extracellular layer formed during *in vitro* culture. Initially, hASCs were seeded in TCPS coverslips overnight at a density of 3.5×10^3 cells well⁻¹ in BM. After, cells were treated with BM and OS-Dex containing free Naringin or Naringin-loaded polymeric nanomicelles at different concentrations. Cells were incubated for 14 days and differentiation medium was exchanged every 3 to 4 days. After each timepoint, cells were fixed as aforementioned and rinsed in dPBS. For immunostaining, cells were first incubated with 0.5 % Triton-X100 in dPBS for 5 min, at RT. Afterwards, cells were rinsed in dPBS and incubated with a 5 % FBS/dPBS blocking solution for 45 min, at RT. Then, cells were washed in dPBS

and incubated with 20 μ L of a mouse anti-human OPN antibody solution (dilution 1:100 in 5% FBS/dPBS; Biolegend, Taper, Sintra, Portugal) overnight at 4°C, in the dark. Cells were then washed with dPBS and incubated with 20 μ L of an anti-mouse Alexa Fluor 647 conjugate dye solution (dilution 1:100 in 5 % FBS/dPBS) for 1 h, at RT, in the dark. Finally, cells were rinsed three times in dPBS before incubating for 5 min with 20 μ L of a DAPI solution for nuclei staining (dilution 1:500, original aliquot at 5 mg mL⁻¹ in H₂O), in the dark, at RT. Cells fluorescence microscopy analysis was performed in a Axio Imager M2 widefield microscope (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH). Image processing was performed by using ZEN v2.3 blue edition. For OPN quantification, 6 random coverslip regions were imaged by using the 10x/0.25 NA Plan-Achromat objective.

Alizarin Red S Mineralization Assay: In order to detect mineral accumulation in osteogenic cells, staining with Alizarin Red S dye was performed. For Alizarin Red S staining, hASCs were seeded overnight in 48-well TCPS coverslips at a density of 3.5 x 10³ cells well⁻¹ (n=3) in BM. Cells were treated with BM and OS-Dex containing free Naringin or Naringin-loaded polymeric nanomicelles at different concentrations. Cells were incubated for 21 days and differentiation medium was exchanged every 3 to 4 days. Afterwards, cells were fixed and washed as aforementioned, before incubation with 300 μ L of Alizarin Red S (40 mM, pH = 4.2), for 1 h in the dark at RT. After incubation, the staining solution was removed and cells were rinsed three times with deionized water. Stained monolayers were imaged with a Stemi 508 Stereo Microscope.

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained is expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (s.d.). One-way ANOVA was used to determine the significant differences among groups, followed by a Newman-Keuls multiple comparison post-hoc test for pairwise comparison. Two-way ANOVA was used for statistical analysis between two groups, where p < 0.05 was considered significant. Significant differences were analyzed by GraphPad Prism version 6.01.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Figure 1. (A) Synthesis of mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer and formulation of Naringin- loaded nanomicelles via nanoprecipitation. Physicochemical characterization of blank (B, D) and Naringin-loaded (C, E) mPEG-MS-PLA micelles via DLS (B, C) and STEM (D, E) techniques. STEM micrographs were obtained at 20 kV and showcase the morphology of (D, D₁) blank micelles and (E, E₁) Naringin-loaded micelles.

Figure 2. Naringin-loaded nanomicelles *in vitro* release profile. Cumulative release profile of Naringin from mPEG-MS-PLA micelles in PBS at pH=7.4 (sphere, blue) and pH=5.5 (triangle, red). Zoomed section represents the cumulative release during the first 4 h of the release studies. Data is presented as mean \pm s.d. (n=3).

Figure 3. Analysis of mPEG-MS-PLA cellular uptake in hASCs. (A-I) Cellular uptake kinetics of nanomicelles (250 pg well⁻¹) obtained via CLSM imaging. Green channel: Coumarin-6-loaded micelles. Red channel: WGA-Alexa Fluor 594 stained cell membrane. White arrows indicate Coumarin-6-loaded micellar carriers. (J, K) FCM analysis of nanomicelles cellular uptake. (J) Representative cellular uptake histograms of micelles in hASCs. M1 marker - represents the gate used for fluorescence intensity quantification. (K) Fluorescent intensity values obtained after incubating hASCs with micelles. Black color represents cell auto-fluorescence; blue: 25 μg; red: 50 μg; and green: 100 μg of incubated micelle dosage. Data is represented as mean ± s.d. (n=3). *p < 0.05.

Figure 4. Naringin-induced ALP activity in OS-Dex (OS) differentiation medium. **(A)** Dose regime schematics of Dex and Naringin administration in this experiment. **(B)** ALP activity of hASCs over 21 days in OS-Dex, with different Naringin concentrations. **(C)** ALP activity fold induction over OS-Dex medium at 14 and 21 days. Differences between Naringin doses and OS-Dex are not significant. **(D)** BCIP/NBT ALP staining at 14 days. **(E)** ALP activity fold induction over OS-Dex medium at 3 and 7 days. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=4). *p < 0.05.

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Figure 5. Naringin-induced BMP-2 secretion in hASCs at 14 and 21 days, after incubation with OS-Dex differentiation medium (OS) control group and with Naringin doses. Cumulative BMP- 2 levels were normalized to DNA content. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. ($n=3$). * $p < 0.05$.

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Figure 6. Naringin-induced osteogenic differentiation and mineralization in hASCs. (A, B) OPN expression in hASCs at 14 days, after incubation with BM and OS-Dex medium (control groups), and with free Naringin, or different Naringin-loaded nanomicelle doses. (A) OPN expressed as fold-induction in MFI relatively to OS control group. (B) Representative fluorescence microscopy imaging of immunostained hASCs at 14 days after incubation with free Naringin or Naringin-loaded nanomicelles at various doses. Blue channel: cell nucleus staining with DAPI. Red channel: OPN staining with anti-mouse Alexa Fluor 647 fluorescent antibody conjugate. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=6), *p < 0.05. (C) Optical microscopy micrographs of Alizarin Red S staining of calcium deposits in Naringin-treated hASCs cell monolayers after a 21-day induction in OS-Dex medium. BM represents basal medium.

Figure 7. The effect of dose regimen and Naringin-loaded micelles on the stimulation of ALP activity in rOS differentiation medium. **(A)** Dose regime of free Naringin and Naringin-loaded micelles in this experiment. **(B)** Comparison of the effect of Naringin-loaded micelles and free Naringin on the promotion of ALP activity in hASCs at 3 days, expressed in fold induction over rOS control group. Comparison of the dose regimen effect of free Naringin **(C)** and Naringin-loaded micelles **(D)** on the promotion of ALP activity in hASCs at 7 days, expressed in fold induction over rOS control group. **(E)** Comparison of the effect of Naringin-loaded micelles and free Naringin with respective dose regimen on the promotion of ALP activity in hASCs at 7 days, expressed in fold induction over rOS control group. **(F, G)** Comparison of the effect of dual administration regime of Naringin-loaded micelles and free Naringin in promoting ALP activity in hASCs at 14 and 21 days, respectively. Levels of ALP activity were normalized to DNA content prior to normalization to rOS control group. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. ($n=4$). * $p < 0.05$.

Naringin is a naturally occurring flavanone with promising potential to bioinstruct stem cells towards osteogenic lineages. Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA nanomicelles administration to human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (hASCs) allowed to rapidly induce hASCs differentiation and augmented the pro-osteogenic effect over that of free drug and standard induction methods, thus indicating their potential to enhance stem cell-based bone regeneration.

Keywords controlled release, human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells, naringin, osteogenic differentiation, polymeric micelles

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Title: Bioinstructive Naringin-loaded Micelles for Guiding Stem Cells Osteodifferentiation

Supporting Information

Bioinstructive Naringin-loaded Micelles for Guiding Stem Cells Osteodifferentiation

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Synthesis and Characterization of mPEG-MS-PLA Copolymer

A highly selective conjugation was accomplished through Michael-type addition reaction between the thiolated polymer (PLA-SH) and the double bond of the N-substituted maleimide group in mPEG-MAL, that resulted in a succinimidyl thioether adduct (Figure S1).^[1]

Figure S1. Synthesis route of mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer via a Michael-type addition. *Phosphate buffer 100 mM, pH = 7.2, containing 5 mM EDTA.

mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer and its reaction components were then characterized by ¹H NMR and ATR-FTIR. The obtained ¹H NMR spectrum of the synthesized copolymer is in agreement with literature reports and exhibit the characteristic peaks of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic blocks (Figure S2). The peaks assigned to mPEG repeating methylene units (c,

O-**CH₂-CH₂**) and methoxy end group (d, **CH₃-O**), respectively at $\delta = 3.63$ and $\delta = 3.37$ ppm, are present in both mPEG-MAL as well mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer spectra.^[2] The multiplet obtained at $\delta = 5.16$ ppm and the single peak at $\delta = 1.57$ ppm are characteristic of the PLA backbone and are present in both PLA-SH as well mPEG-MS-PLA spectra.^[2,3] These peaks correspond to repeating methenyl (a, **CH₃-CH-O**) and methyl (b, **CH₃-CH-O**) units, respectively. Regarding the PLA-SH spectrum, two distinct peaks can be distinguished between $\delta = 4.2 - 4.4$ ppm: one corresponding to the methenyl (g, **CH₃-CH-OH**) proton neighbor of the hydroxyl end group at $\delta = 4.34$ ppm, and the other corresponding to the methylene protons adjacent to the ester linkage closest to the terminal thiol (f, **-O-CH₂-CH₂-SH**) at $\delta = 4.25$ ppm.^[4] In addition, the peak around $\delta = 2.75$ ppm corresponds to the methylene protons adjacent to the thiol end-group (e, **-O-CH₂-CH₂-SH**) confirming that PLA-SH was not oxidated to the disulfide form.^[4] If the disulfide was present a characteristic peak of methylene protons adjacent to disulfides would be present instead at $\delta = 2.9$ ppm as described by Cunningham and Oh.^[4] Finally, the singlet observed at $\delta = 6.70$ ppm on the mPEG-MAL spectrum is assigned to the alkene protons (**CH=CH**) present in the maleimide ring.^[5] The successful coupling mPEG-MS-PLA is further supported by the disappearance of this characteristic peak assigned to the maleimide moiety as well as the appearance of PLA-related resonances on the copolymer spectrum.

Figure S2. ^1H NMR spectra of mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer and its unitary components (mPEG-MAL and PLA-SH) in CDCl_3 .

Adding to NMR characterization, the ATR-FTIR spectra also corroborated the successful conjugation of mPEG-MAL and PLA-SH polymers (**Figure S3**). The initial analysis of the individual polymers reveals a band at 2883 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to **-C-H** stretching vibrations (CH_2 symmetric), and is present in both mPEG-MAL and mPEG-MS-PLA spectra.^[6] Also, the strong band obtained at 1755 cm^{-1} corresponds to the carbonyl (**-C=O**) stretching of lactic acid esters in the PLA-SH polymer.^[7] Regarding mPEG-MAL, the characteristic band obtained at 1711 cm^{-1} is assigned to carbonyl (**-C=O**) stretching of the imide ring (Figure S2, inset).^[8] This maleimide-related band appears as a small shoulder in the copolymer spectrum, corroborating a successful synthesis. Alternatively, the small peak obtained at 696 cm^{-1} in the mPEG-MAL spectrum corresponds to **cis-CH=CH** imide and is reported to be characteristic of unreacted maleimide groups.^[8,9] Therefore, it could be useful for further corroborating the

conjugation of the two polymers. However, this weak band is overlapped in the copolymer spectra with the characteristic PLA bands in the region of 760-650 cm^{-1} . The peak observed in mPEG-MAL at 1466 cm^{-1} corresponds to **-C-H** deformation (CH_2 scissoring), while the peak at 1456 cm^{-1} is assigned to **-CH₃** bending in the PLA-SH spectrum.^[7,10] Both peaks are visibly overlapped in the 1467-1455 cm^{-1} region in the copolymer spectrum (Figure S3).

Figure S3. ATR-FTIR spectra of mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer and its unitary components (mPEG-MAL and PLA-SH).

In addition, the spectra of PLA-SH and mPEG-MS-PLA copolymer exhibited a characteristic band at 1184 cm^{-1} which is assigned to **-C-O** bending in lactic acid esters.^[11] The **-C-O-C** ether asymmetric stretching vibrations present in both PEG and PLA overlap in the range 1150 to 1040 cm^{-1} .^[6,7] The bands at 959 and 962 cm^{-1} correspond to **-CH₂** rocking (**CH₂-CH₂-O**) in mPEG-MAL and mPEG-MS-PLA copolymer, respectively, further confirming the presence of the mPEG backbone in the final copolymer.^[10] Taken together, both characterization techniques establish the successful conjugation of the two monomers, resulting in the mPEG-MS-PLA copolymer. This synthesis alternative not only allows for facile production of a reproducible mPEG-MS-PLA diblock copolymer, but can also be carried out under mild reaction conditions.

Colloidal Stability of Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA Nanomicelles
 Figure S4. Colloidal stability of mPEG-MS-PLA nanomicelles in aqueous conditions: water (sphere, blue) and PBS at pH 7.4 (square, black). (A) Particle size (nm), (B) PDI and (C) ζ -potential (mV).

Naringin Calibration Curve in Water

Figure S5. (A) Naringin calibration curve in water calculated by measuring the absorbance

peak at $\lambda = 282$ nm, ranging from 2 to 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. (A₁) Inset represents the absorbance spectrum of Naringin within a spectral window from 250 to 370 nm.

Figure S6. Characterization of Coumarin-6 loaded mPEG-MS-PLA micelles. (A) DLS analysis of Coumarin-6 micelles. (B) Fluorescence micrograph of Coumarin-6 micelles. Green channel: Coumarin-6.

Cellular uptake and intracellular trafficking

Figure S7. Confocal laser scanning (CLSM) micrographs of Coumarin-6 micelles uptake in hASCs at 4 h following incubation. (A) 3D CLSM reconstruction of the cell volume. (B) Orthogonal projection of nanomicelles internalization in hASCs. Blue channel: Hoescht 33342 labelled nucleus, Green channel: Coumarin-6, Red channel: WGA-Alexa 594® labelled cells. White arrows indicate nanomicelles. (C to E) Intracellular trafficking and colocalization analysis of nanomicelles in lysosomal compartments at different time points. Blue channel: Hoescht 33342 labelled nucleus, Green channel: Coumarin-6, Red channel: LysoTracker® Deep Red. White arrows indicate micelles-lysosome colocalization hotspots.

Figure S8. Characterization of free Naringin (A), blank (B) and Naringin-loaded mPEG-MS-PLA micelles (C) effect in hASCs cell viability following incubation at different time points. BM represents basal medium negative cytotoxicity (K-) control. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=5). n.s. stands for non-significant, *p 0.05.

Biocompatibility and Cell Proliferation Assays

Figure S9. Effect of free Naringin on the proliferation of hASCs relative to the negative control, basal medium (BM) after to 24, 48 and 72 h of incubation. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=5). *p < 0.05.

Cytotoxicity Assay for Naringin Dose Regimen Studies

Figure S10. Quantification of dsDNA content after One dose and Two dose free Naringin regimen experiments, normalized to rOS control group. rOS represents the osteogenic control group. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=4). n.s. stands for non-significant.

Figure S11. Naringin-loaded micelles induced BMP-2 secretion in hASCs at 14 and 21 days, after incubation with osteogenic differentiation medium (rOS) control group and with different Naringin doses. Cumulative BMP-2 levels were normalized to DNA content. Data is represented as mean \pm s.d. (n=3). *p < 0.05.

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